

Effectiveness Of Social Media In Services Marketing With Special Reference To Healthcare Products

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Abstract. Services marketing means the marketing of the intangibility i.e. perishable in nature, unlike product marketing, services marketing focuses on the values of the customers, and marketers aim to increase the trust among consumers of their products. Services which include, telecommunication, hospitality, health and wellness, consulting, etc., are the role-playing service industries in the country, as we already know, services are intangible and perishable, it needs to be marketed effectively and efficiently in order to maintain the balance in the marketing objectives, for that today's marketers use social media as a tool to accomplish their services marketing objectives, social media is a powerful tool nowadays, which is very fast, effective in communication aspects, due to those benefits marketers using social media to acquire new consumers and retain the existing customers. The services in healthcare products are very essential and it needs to be effectively carried out in order to satisfy the consumers because the person who orders healthcare products will be needed that product for immediate usage. The usage of social media here in services marketing of healthcare products will be a great tool for marketers in reaching their target consumers easily. In this paper, the researchers elucidate how social media is effectively used by services marketers of healthcare products, in order to satisfy consumers, for data collection researchers use primary data collected from consumers through google forms, and secondary data collected from previously published articles, thesis and journals.

Keywords: Services Marketing, Social Media, Health Care products, Digital Marketing.

1. Introduction

Services marketing is a type of marketing used by companies that offer a service to their Consumers to enhance brand mindfulness and profit. Services marketing, as opposed to product marketing, focuses on advertising impalpable relations that bring value to Consumers. Advertisers use successful service marketing styles to gain the trust of their Consumers and demonstrate how their products may profit them. Businesses' service marketing tactics may be grounded on the creation of generalities, advantages, and promises to help them to vend their services.

2. Difference between Product Marketing and Services Marketing

1. Tangible Products & Intangible Services

Because advertising can readily show and illustrate how palpable effects operate, they may be easier to promote than impalpable services. It may also make it easier for buyers to attribute financial value to physical goods. Because services are impalpable, advertisers constantly concentrate on promoting the people who offer the service and developing connections with implicit Consumers. This can prop in the development of trust and the generation of deals.

2. Customization

Unlike products, which are constantly produced in one way and also vended to Consumers, businesses may conform their services to match the specific demands of each client. For illustration, a establishment that provides digital marketing services may conform whatever platforms it concentrates on to the specific demands of each client. As a marketer, you may emphasise this by concentrating on how you can alter service to better fit a wide variety of different Consumers.

3. Power

When a buyer buys goods, they come the proprietor of it. This implies they may continue to use the

product for as long as they want and resale it if they want. When a consumer buys a service, the company keeps the workers, chops, and capabilities that supplied the service. While product marketing may concentrate on why a buyer wants to buy a certain item, service marketing concentrates on developing the brand and personality of the service provider.

4. Trust

Consumers who are displeased with a product can return it; still, Consumers who are displeased with a service can not return it once they've used it. This is why services marketing focuses considerably on establishing trust with Consumers and maintaining an exceptional client experience with each connection with its target followership. Service- grounded businesses likewise want to keep their consumers satisfied so they will continue to use their services.

5. Time

Businesses frequently deliver services to Consumers at a certain time or for a specific length of time. Consumers must also renew the service agreement in order to continue entering the service. A consumer, on the other hand, may buy a thing formerly and use it constantly. As a result, rather than dealing a product formerly, services marketing frequently focuses on dealing subscriptions, generating recommendations, and keeping consumers.

6. Market Size

The Markey size for service- grounded enterprises may be lower than that of product- grounded enterprises. This is because utmost enterprises can shoot particulars to Consumers each over the world, but numerous businesses only serve a certain geographic zone.

Social Media is a important tool in services marketing, in this paper, how social media is used as an effective tool to negotiate the objects of marketers in health care products.

Social Media in Marketing

The development of social media marketing(SMM) from a standalone tool to a multifaceted origin of digital marketing on an decreasingly significant and growing followership is being driven by marketers across diligence, with over 80 of buyers reporting that social media, especially influencer content, explosively impacts buying opinions.

Social media marketing is connecting with your followership using social media platforms in order to develop your brand, boost deals, and enhance website business. This includes creating compelling content for your social media runners, interacting with your followers, tracking your progress, and executing social media advertisements.

Social media is being used by businesses in a wide variety of ways. For case, a company concerned about what consumers are saying about its brand might follow social media conversations and respond to material references(social media listening and engagement). A company would use an analytics tool to examine its reach, engagement, and deals on social media to determine how well it's performing there(social media analytics). largely targeted social media announcements would be used by a company looking to reach a certain population on a large scale(social media advertising).

Marketing of Healthcare Products & Services

Because healthcare deals with health behaviours rather than simply copping habits, marketing healthcare services and products give special problems compared to selling other consumer goods and services. Health marketing entails spreading knowledge and raising mindfulness, but it also involves changing gestures, which is gruelling and can take time. A changing population and associated issues, technological developments in the field of drug, and other outside variables all have an impact on healthcare marketing.

Understanding the Demographic profile of the consumers using healthcare products

Population changes have an impact on not just how you promote healthcare products and services, but also what's retailed, depending on where you operate. For case, if people live longer, businesses may decide to develop goods and services specifically for an aged population or for their adult children furnishing care. also, different ethnical groups may have colourful health issues. Healthcare marketers must be careful to make marketing strategies acclimatized for colourful demographics since different groups by age, race, and profitable position respond to colourful marketing dispatches or venues.

Calculating the Trends of Consumers using Healthcare products

Despite the fact that the causes may be complicated, people can change health behaviours for a variety of

reasons, which makes marketing delicate. For case, despite data demonstrating the dangerous consequences of inordinate sun exposure, colourful age groups reply else. The duty of marketers is to comprehend why maybe youthful people get smelled into a trend of visiting tanning conventions, allowing that this is safer than exposure to the sun outside. profitable trends can also have an impact on healthy behaviours like buying tradition medicines or outfit like glucose testing accoutrements for diabetes.

Preparation of Policies for Healthcare Consumers:

Healthcare marketers need to be aware of the effects that government health laws and regulations may have on marketing initiatives. For instance, changes to health insurance rules may impact how people access preventative or urgent treatment. Removing the need for a prescription for popular medications might make them more accessible to individuals, but the cost of buying them over-the-counter may subsequently be prohibitive for others, or there may be worries about the abuse of a product without a doctor's prescription, necessitating more education. For some communities, the new government dietary recommendations for healthy eating or disease prevention may be challenging.

Taking Care of the Privacy of Healthcare consumers:

In healthcare marketing, privacy is of utmost importance, especially for marketers working for healthcare organisations like hospitals or clinics. You must be aware of and carefully abide by privacy regulations, including the permissible and prohibited uses of patient health information for commercial purposes. For other marketers, like those working for a company that produces healthcare products, research will help you craft your marketing messages to convey sensitivity.

3. Literature Review:

- 1) The concept of convenience, according to **Brown, L. G. (1990)**, has not been fully defined and operationalized by managers and should be viewed as multidimensional. provides a conceptual framework for considering how convenient services are, allowing for the identification of strategic and tactical marketing possibilities. discusses how this framework's consequences for managers. Reviews a consumer product marketing paradigm from a different publication and applies it to service marketing.
- 2) **Tansuhaj, P., McCullough, J., & Randall (1988)** explains Employees are crucial to recruiting, establishing, and keeping connections with clients in services marketing. Internal marketing programmes with a significant focus on employee development have emerged as a result of the understanding of the essential role that workers play in service marketing. The relationship between internal marketing initiatives (aimed at hiring, educating, inspiring, motivating, and retaining employees) and more conventional external marketing initiatives are examined in this study. Service managers may improve customer loyalty, contentment, and perception of quality by looking at how the core components of the services marketing management model—internal and external marketing, staff attitudes and behaviour, and customer attitudes and behaviour—relate to one another.
- 3) **Khan, I. (2022)** The current study investigates relationships between social media marketing activities (SMMA), brand experience, purchase intention, and attitude toward the company in light of the growing interest in the part that SMMA play in a brand's ability to deliver superior experiences. The customer involvement level (high vs. low) and customer generation (Millennials vs. Non-Millennials) are also evaluated in this study as mediators in the relationship between SMMA and brand experience. The findings point to SMMA's crucial contribution to brand experience, purchasing intention, and attitude toward the brand. The findings show that the relationship between SMMA and brand experience differs depending on the customer's engagement level with the brand's SMMA (high vs. low) and consumer generation (Millennials vs. Non-Millennials). These findings help marketers understand how the link between SMMA and brand experience is influenced by customer generation and level of involvement.
- 4) **Guerra, F., Linz et.al (2022)** Social media (SoMe) has grown in popularity among therapists as a professional tool and as a means of contact in daily life. The majority of respondents claimed to be passive users of SoMe. LinkedIn was the SoMe platform that was utilised the most, however, usage varied between nations. According to respondents, one benefit of SoMe is the opportunity to be informed about the latest articles. The respondents emphasised the loss of human interaction, the inability to receive "hands-on" training, and the lack of control over the calibre of scientific evidence when discussing the drawbacks of SoMe. Social media is being utilised more and more in the workplace for networking, case-based learning, and scientific update.
- 5) **H. Ryu, W. Pratt, and (2022)** This study was out to show how looking at social media posts might reveal microaggressions and provide fresh cultural perceptions. We investigate the reasons behind Korean women's reluctance to receive recommended gynaecological care and how microaggressions

that are apparent on social media provide information on how to combat such damaging messages. According to our analysis, mothers, male partners, and social media users who appear to be supportive are the main causes of pre- and post-visit microaggressions directed at unmarried women seeking gynaecological care, while healthcare professionals are only responsible for mid-visit microaggressions. The repression of women's health care was also shown to be reinforced via social media, as we recently revealed.

- 6) **Kordzadeh, N., & Young, D. K. (2022)** Businesses and charitable groups now use social media as a strategic tool to engage with customers. However, there isn't a complete structure in place to facilitate the ongoing development of social media results. This work builds on earlier research on user interaction and social media analytics to provide a comprehensive, analytics-driven approach to creating and refining social content strategies. The approach gives businesses a series of steps to follow in order to routinely evaluate their own content subject posting efforts as well as those of rivals. The process for measuring the impact of content subjects and post attributes on engagement results is then described. The resulting insights are then used to guide future posting actions. To show the viability of the suggested approach, a proof-of-concept instance involving healthcare is provided.

4. Research Methodology:

Researchers used both Primary and Secondary data for this research. Primary data was collected using google forms circulated through social media and received 184 usable fully filled questionnaires. Secondary data was collected through various websites, blogs, theses and research articles. Researchers used SPSS to calculate Frequency Distribution, one sample t-Test and One-Way ANOVA to analyse the collected data.

Objectives of the Research:

1. To understand the effectiveness of social media in healthcare marketing.
2. To analyse the satisfaction level of services marketing in consumer healthcare products.
3. To find which factor is the most influencing factor of healthcare services marketing.

Scope of the Research:

This research is mainly concerned with the effectiveness of social media in healthcare services marketing. This will help fellow scholars or marketers who are doing an in-depth consumer survey regarding this topic.

Limitations of the Research:

This research is carried over only in Chennai City, Tamil Nadu, India, the same research will give different results if the survey is conducted after some years because it is based on the demand and necessity of the healthcare consumers.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

Table 1 showing demographic profile of the Healthcare Consumers

S. No	Demographic Profile	Freq.	Valid Percent	Cumm. Percent	
1	Gender	Male	100	54	54
		Female	84	46	100
2	Age	Less than 20	4	2	2
		21-30	96	52	54
		31-40	64	35	89
		41-50	20	11	100
		Above 50	0	0	100
3	Annual Family Income	Less than 2,00,000	4	2	2
		2,00,001 – 4,00,000	156	85	87
		4,00,001 – 6,00,000	24	13	100
		Above 6,00,000	0	0	100
4	Marital Status	Married	68	37	37
		Unmarried	116	63	100

From the above Table 1, the demographic profile of the healthcare consumers are discussed, Male consumers are more in number (54%), age group between 21-30 are the major healthcare consumers (52%), 85% of the healthcare consumers belongs to the annual family income of Rs. 2,00,001 – 4,00,000, 63% of the respondents are unmarried.

Table 2 showing one-way ANOVA between AGE and other factors

		Sum Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Frequency of Purchase	Between Groups	13.336	3	4.445	8.376	.000
	Within Groups	95.533	180	.531		
	Total	108.870	183			
Mode of Purchase	Between Groups	7.066	3	2.355	16.971	.000
	Within Groups	12.768	92	.139		
	Total	19.833	95			
Preferred Social Media	Between Groups	11.119	3	3.706	2.176	.092
	Within Groups	306.533	180	1.703		
	Total	317.652	183			

H₀ – There is no Significant relationship between Age and Factors such as Frequency of Purchase, Mode of Purchase, Preferred Social Media.

H₁ – There is a Significant relationship between Age and Factors such as Frequency of Purchase, Mode of Purchase, Preferred Social Media.

From the above Table 2, showing the analysis of one-way ANOVA between Age and other factors such as Frequency of Purchase, Mode of Purchase, Preferred Social Media, in the factor named Frequency of Purchase, there is a significant relationship between Age and Frequency of Healthcare purchases, (.000), it shows that not all age group of healthcare consumers are equally purchasing the healthcare products/services. In the factor named Mode of purchase, there is a significant relationship between Age and Mode of healthcare purchase made, (.000), it shows that not all age group of healthcare consumers are making purchase evenly, in the factor named Preferred social media, there is no significant relationship between Age and Social media usage preferences (.092), it shows that all the age group of healthcare consumers are equally using all type social media.

Table 3 showing one sample t-Test of the factors influencing Healthcare consumers Satisfaction

	N	Mean	Std. Dev.	Std. Error	t-value	Rank
Effectiveness of SMM Adv.	184	1.20	.577	.043	28.101	6
Responses from Marketers	184	1.63	.819	.060	26.991	7
After Sales Services	184	1.35	.599	.044	30.504	3
Fast Delivery	184	1.54	.499	.037	41.918	1
Privacy Protection	184	1.33	.593	.044	30.314	4
Online Live Support	184	1.54	.715	.053	29.267	5
Prices and Offers	184	1.41	.536	.040	35.749	2

From the above one sample t-test analysis, it is clear that there are four important key factors which influencing the healthcare consumers to purchase via social media services marketing strategies. The mean ranges from 1.20 to 1.63 which shows, all factors are ranges from highly satisfied to satisfied category for healthcare consumers, based on the t value the factors are ranked, Fast Delivery is the most important key factor for healthcare consumers while using social media for purchasing, (t value = 41.918, Rank 1), prices and offers holds the second rank (t value = 35.749, Rank 2), followed by After sales services (t value = 30.504, Rank 3) and Privacy protection (t value = 30.314, Rank 4), the other factors such as Online Live support (t value = 29.267, Rank 5), Effectiveness of Social media marketing advertisements (t value = 28.101, Rank 6) and Responses from Marketers (t value = 26.991, Rank 7) respectively.

5. Conclusion:

From the above data analysis and secondary data analysis, the authors conclude that social media services marketing is sufficiently effective for healthcare consumers in fulfilling their needs and wants timely. Objective 1, Social media is effective enough to satisfy all healthcare consumers, objective 2, Healthcare consumers are ranges between highly satisfied and satisfied category (Mean ranges from 1.20 to 1.63), Objective 3, key factors influencing the healthcare consumers' satisfaction, they are namely Fast Delivery (t value = 41.918), Prices and offers (t value = 35.749), After Sales Services (t value = 30.504) and Privacy

Protection (t value = 30.314). The conclusion of this study will be helpful for digital marketers, research scholars, and business people.

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